

"Are there differences in Career Preferences between Education and Teacher Training Program Students in Java and Outside Java?"

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Abstract

Career preference is a person's tendency towards a career. This study investigates whether there are differences in career preferences between students with a background in education and teacher study programs in universities on the island of Java and outside the island of Java. The students involved came from 20 universities in Indonesia, both public and private universities. The instrument in collecting this data used a career preference questionnaire with a sample of 128 students. The questionnaire instrument was constructed by the researcher by conducting content validity by 5 experts using Alpha Cronbach and continued with construct validity with Exploratory Factor Analysis. So that the final questionnaire instrument consists of 28 statement items related to career preferences and 1 question item related to career choices. The results of the study found that there was no significant difference between the career preferences of students at tertiary institutions in Java and outside Java.

Keywords: *career preference, Java, outside Java, t-test*

INTRODUCTION

Career development is a fundamental concept for people because it defines them as unique individuals and promotes social growth and personal well-being by fostering a healthy balance between personal and professional lives (Ornovetchii., 2023). A successful career precedes various other career and life outcomes, such as self-concept, reactions from the workplace, well-being and health, and withdrawal (Spurk, et al., 2018). Career decision-making anxiety and self-efficacy are positively correlated with future temporal perspective, with emotion spin serving as a moderating factor (Jung, et al., 2015).

An individual's choice of career will determine whether their life is meaningful or unworthwhile, enjoyable or disappointing, or honorable or abhorrent (MacAskill, 2014). People's professional choices are influenced by a variety of factors, including controllable, external, and personal influences (Brewer, 2018). But, the most important aspect in choosing a career is one's attitude toward stable employment, which is followed by personality-centered attitudes toward risk-taking and social interaction, as well as integration of lifestyles, autonomy, and service (Lukyanchenko).

Through a discourse of authentic selfhood, young people overcome employment uncertainty and defend their decision to pursue a degree that does not have a clear career consequence (James, et al., 2020). The way in which young people perceive their place in the labor market and their future opportunities influences their job-seeking behavior, and they give explanations for their decisions that are based on logic, emotion, and life values (Ylistö, 2018). Ultimately, the majority of young

individuals base their employment decisions on their passions or areas of interest, job security, and fair compensation (Pradeep, 2019).

For example, when it comes to job planning, young individuals from less affluent families typically exhibit reflexivity and choose vocations based more on social conventions than on aptitude (Laughland-Booÿ, et al., 2015). Meanwhile, adolescents from families with businesses determine professional decisions based on their personalities, gender, sense of belonging to the family business, and expectations of their parents' jobs (Schröder, et al., 2011). Young people's career choices are influenced by factors such as residing in metropolitan locations, having a family background, receiving high-quality labor training, and being part of a company agglomeration (Tran, et al., 2017).

Students' career choices at higher education institutions are influenced by both internal and external influences, in addition to interpersonal factors (Mohamed, et al., 2022). According to Malik et al (2018), the decision of a career is heavily influenced by extrinsic and interpersonal variables, but intrinsic motivation is not so significant. On the other hand, on a teaching career, the most important factor influencing decisions is intrinsic variables, while program of study, age, and gender are also important considerations (Bhattacharya & Raju, 2019).

Students with backgrounds in education and teaching are influenced by several circumstances to seek occupations beyond their fields of study. There are main reasons for not choosing a teaching career are negative learning experience, task approach skills, outlook and future directions (Suryani & George, 2021). In addition, the need to acquire a new occupational position and self-image, workplace shifts, and the desire to pursue capital are the main reasons why students with backgrounds in education and teaching choose employment outside of their disciplines (Smith, 2018).

On the contrary, there are many other factors that influence a person's decision to become a teacher, including personal preferences and a cursory understanding of the abilities of educators, communication, planning, and cooperation (Bobocea, 2023; Bohndick, et al., 2017). Additionally, the social utility ideals and dedication to the teaching profession are the primary reasons teacher applicants choose to become teachers (Dündar, 2014). When compared to other explanations, altruistic-intrinsic motivations obtained the highest mean, which explains why the majority of pre-service teachers chose to become teachers (Noor, et al., 2021).

In Indonesia, there are more than 4600 universities, of which 68% are private and 32% are public institutions (Ronald & Emmerich, 2022). The quality and quantity of higher education are the main topics of discussion in Indonesia, which raises a strategic question between the two (Digdowiseiso, 2020). Indonesian higher education institutions often aim for improved quality by raising their standards nationally and internationally and focusing on the future (Kumang & Ahman, 2020).

Educational and teacher study programs are spread across the universities. Those with higher education who are between the ages of 25 and 64 have a relatively low employment rate (OECD, 2023). But given this requirement for college graduates, how relevant are preferences in terms of how well education and teacher education program students' backgrounds fit for their future careers? This research aims to answer the question: Are there differences in career preferences between students with educational and teacher education backgrounds in Java Island and outside Java Island?

METHOD

This research is quantitative descriptive research. Descriptive research seeks to describe the current status of identified variables or phenomena (Cooper & Endacott, 2007). Data collection was conducted using a questionnaire instrument. The questionnaire instrument was self-constructed by the researcher related to student career preferences using a Likert scale of 1 to 4. Scale 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = agree, and 4 = strongly agree. The questionnaire items submitted to the trial respondents consisted of 33 statement items and 1 question item. Then content validity was carried out by involving 5 experts and using the Cronbach Alpha formula (the minimum Cronbach Alpha value on each item must be 0.80 with a significance error of 5%). From the content validity, 5 items were found to be invalid.

Furthermore, construct validity was carried out on a test sample of 71 students from various teacher education study programs from 2 State Universities, namely in Yogyakarta and Bengkulu. The collected data were then analyzed with Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). A multivariate statistical technique called exploratory factor analysis is used for the development and validation of psychological theories and measures. It is also suitable for identifying latent factors in surveys with Likert scales (Watkins, 2018; Schreiber, 2020). The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value shows 0.790 (> 0.50) and the significance level is < 0.05 . This shows that it has met the assumption test. For the scree plot display can be seen in figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Scree Plot of EFA of Career Preference Instrument

From the results of the analysis through the scree plot, from the student career preference questionnaire instrument, 7 factors were formed. The items that represent these factors based on the results of the rotated component matrix can be seen in the Appendix. The results of the analysis show that there are 2 items whose value on the rotated component matrix is below 0.50 so they are not included in taking career preference data on the research sample.

The soft skills measurement sample used convenience sampling technique (Saunders, et al., 2012), which consisted of 128 people who were students from 20 public and private universities in Indonesia. This research sample consists of undergraduate students from teacher education majors or pre-service teacher professional education programs (PPG). Data was obtained in November 2023. The following table shows the distribution of the research sample:

Table 1. Distribution of student soft skills measurement samples

Region	Number of Campuses	Sample
Java Island	7	64
Outer Java Island	13	64
Total	20	128

After that, the questionnaire was rearranged by discarding the invalid items and then distributed to respondents for measurement. The purpose of this investigation is to determine how much each student values a particular career path. Furthermore, the collected soft skills measurement results were analyzed with a two-sample T-test statistical test to see the differences in career preferences between students in Java and Outer Java. A statistical approach known as two sample t-test is used

to determine whether the means of two independent populations differ or not (Liang, et al., 2019). Before being analyzed with a two-sample t-test, the data from the Likert scale questionnaire will first be transformed into an interval scale (*Method of Successive Interval (MSI)*).

RESULT

In Levene's Test of equality of variances, the significance value is found to be 0,157 which means it is greater than 0,05. This means that it has fulfilled the homogeneity assumption test or the variances of the two groups are the same. Because the variances of the two groups are equal, we can use the assumption of equal variances (equal variances assumed) for the two-sample independent t test.

In the significance value (2-tailed), the P value is 0.671 (>0.05) which means it is much greater than the significance level. Thus, there is no significant difference between the career preferences of students in Java and outside Java. More information can be seen in table 2 below:

Table 2. Independent two sample t-test of career preference

	<i>Lavene's test for Equality of variances</i>					<i>T-test for Equality of means</i>		<i>95% Confidence interval of the difference</i>	
	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig (2-tailed)</i>	<i>Mean difference</i>	<i>Std. Error difference</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>
<i>Equal variances assumed</i>	2,026	0,157	0,426	126	0,671	0,965	2,264	-3,516	5,446
<i>Equal variances not assumed</i>			0,426	115,347	0,671	0,965	2,264	-3,52	5,45

The career preferences of students on the island of Java appear to be only slightly higher with an average of 76.43 compared to the career preferences of students outside Java (mean = 75.46). As more information can be seen in table 3.

Table 3. Average of student career preference

Group	Sample	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Java	64	76,43	10,69	1,34
Outside of Java	64	75,46	14,63	1,83

Furthermore, to identify the careers chosen by most students with a background in education and teacher study programs, a percentage analysis was carried out on 1 item that they had answered. The percentage results can be seen in figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Career choices of higher education students with a background in education and teacher study programs

In figure 2, it shows that with a background in education and teacher study programs, the majority of them still choose their future careers as teachers (44%) or lecturers (26%). As many as 16% of them prefer to work in other sectors but still related to their educational background. In contrast, the least popular career choices are becoming a content creator, data scientist/data analyst, and working in other sectors that are not related to the background of the study program they have undergone.

DISCUSSION

The answer to the main question of this study, namely are there differences in career preferences between students of education and teacher study programs in Java and outside Java? It can be

answered according to the results of the analysis of the research results that there is no significant difference in career preferences between the two groups. This contradicts the results of other studies that compare the career preferences of one group with another. Longva & Strand (2018) explained the results of their research that students that are internationally oriented and those who are regionally oriented have different career preferences. Likewise, research by Chawla et al (2017) compared the career preferences of 3 groups, namely senior generation, generation X, and generation Y. The three generations under study differ significantly in terms of their preferences for careers and levels of work participation. Even more, job preferences vary significantly between nations and generations; Sweden places a higher weight on soft skills, whilst Italy and India place a higher value on extrinsic factors like security and salary (Camasso & Jagannathan, 2021).

However, the differences in the results of this study may be due to various factors. Extraversion, conscientiousness, and openness to new experiences are examples of personality qualities that affect occupational role preferences and how they are expressed (Jong et al., 2019). In addition, the relative relevance of job characteristics and an individual's ability to compromise are two factors that impact high preference cohesion, which is favorably connected with career decision-making (Shimoni, et al., 2019). However, as explained in the introduction, individual and contextual factors account for most differences in profession preferences; in more unequal societies, both intrinsic and extrinsic values hold greater significance (Esser & Lindh, 2018). Career preferences based on aspects are dependable and steady, remaining constant over time and both within and between cultures (Gutentag & Gati, 2016).

Based on the survey results, the career choices chosen by students are still relevant to their current scientific fields, namely education and teaching. Most of them prefer to become teachers or lecturers in the future. In the results of other studies, students' capacity to choose a career is greatly influenced by their family history and sense of self-efficacy, but not by their age or gender (Galliot, et al., 2015). However, this career choice to become a teacher according to Wang & Wang (2022) is motivated by a desire for self-actualization and an altruistic desire to help and impact young people; intrinsic rewards balance concerns about status, salary, and effort.

CONCLUSION AND LIMITATION

Research on career preferences between teacher education and training program students in Java and outside Java still has limitations. Especially in terms of sample size which is still relatively

small. Therefore, future research is expected to have sufficient and representative samples from Java and outside Java. Even, if possible, the sample has representation in each province. Hence, it appears that there is a significant difference or not in these career preferences.

The main conclusions of this study are: 1) The results of the EFA analysis of the career preference instrument that has been made (questionnaire) form 7 components, and 2) There is no significant difference between the career preferences of students with educational and teacher education backgrounds both on the island of Java and outside the island of Java.

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Appendix

Table 4. Items Representing the Factors of the Student Career Preference Instrument

No. Item		Component						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	<i>I choose a job that provides flexibility in working hours</i>	0,782						
2	<i>I choose a job that allows me to help others</i>	0,769						
3	<i>I choose a job that hones my problem-solving skills</i>	0,743						
4	<i>I choose a job where I have a good relationship with my leader</i>	0,742						
5	<i>I choose a job where I feel that every worker can make a difference to the company</i>	0,726						
6	<i>I choose a job that gives me many benefits</i>	0,725						
7	<i>I choose a job that emphasizes the balance between work and life outside of work (work-life balance)</i>	0,701						
8	<i>I choose a job where I can make a</i>	0,645						

	<i>positive impact</i>							
9	<i>I choose a job that makes my social life better</i>	0,558						
10	<i>I tend not to choose a workplace that has security</i>		0,789					
11	<i>I tend to avoid jobs that provide training and development to their employees</i>		0,741					
12	<i>I choose a job that is reluctant to provide financial rewards.</i>		0,721					
13	<i>I choose a job that does not train skills and expertise for its employees</i>		0,603					
14	<i>I choose a job that is willing to give me a high salary</i>			0,862				
15	<i>I choose a workplace that provides high salaries to its employees</i>			0,815				
16	<i>I choose a job that gives me autonomy over what I want to do</i>				0,745			
17	<i>I will work in a company/workplace that has been successful</i>				0,707			
18	<i>I choose a job that gives me inner satisfaction when I work</i>				0,692			
19	<i>I choose a job depending on the company's image</i>				0,638			
20	<i>The dominant profession in my extended family influences me in determining the career field I will pursue</i>					0,825		
21	<i>I chose my job because I saw that many of my friends wanted to go to that company/workplace</i>					0,783		
22	<i>I chose a certain job because of my parents' encouragement</i>					0,729		
23	<i>I choose a job that provides a proportional workload</i>						0,791	
24	<i>I am interested in working by receiving</i>						0,768	

	<i>interesting tasks</i>							
25	<i>I choose a job that recognizes the performance of its employees.</i>							0,754
26	<i>I choose a job that provides rewards and welfare for its employees</i>							0,608

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